

THE ROLE OF NON-STANDARD LANGUAGE UNITS IN LANGUAGE SYSTEM

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Annotation: The article deals with the significance of using nonstandard language units in English. The practical usage and role of these units are discussed in this article. The article describes general characteristics of language units ; such as argot, slang and jargon and specific priorities in language. It indicates the importance of utilizing them and their meaning and shows the limit of them according to some particular reasons. The purpose of article is to learn the ideas of great scholars around the world and define the difference between standard and nonstandard language units.

Key words: modification, different circumstances, accelerate, acceptable expressions, comparative and explanatory dictionary, rapid emergence of new slangs, lexically and stylistically heterogeneous, stratified groups of society.

Introduction. Each language has its own rich linguistic tools. The total number of words in a language constitutes its lexicon, i.e. vocabulary. Lexicology (from Greek *lexikos* - dictionary and *logos* - teaching) is a branch of linguistics that examines the composition of linguistic units. The vocabulary of the language and the words that make it up have a number of commonalities. They are noticeable in the following:

- 1) words in the language have the characteristic of expressing a certain meaning. The semantic features of the word are organized in the section of lexicology called semiosiology;
- 2) the changes that occur during the development of any language are firstly reflected in its lexicon. Because during the development of society, the language is enriched with new words, while some words become old and gradually fall out of use;
- 3) the words in the vocabulary of the language are also distinguished by whether they are limited or not limited according to the level of consumption.

Non-standard language units are slang, argot, jargon , dialectism, professionalism and others. We look through them in detail. Slang is a change or modification of standard language. If you look carefully, you can find different types of slang. For example, slang can be created by combining several words, for example, with the help of borrowings from slang, abbreviations (mike, ok), onomatopoeia (boom, fuck). foreign languages (samurai, driver), as well as by analogy (bet, pick up). Different types of slang arise for different reasons and under different circumstances. One of the common methods is the emergence of new words and phrases in one professional group. For example, students say "unsuccessful", "super". Motorists call their cars "four", "nine". But it should be remembered that slang words often used by one group may have different meanings in other groups. Certain conditions accelerate the emergence of new words. For example, the formation of new groups, which include representatives of different people and different nationalities, leads to the rapid emergence of new slangs. For example, in the armed forces: "walkie-talkie", "demobilization". Sometimes a new word comes up with one person and the rest pick it up. In many cases, new expressions that were once associated with slang eventually find their way into dictionaries. The dictionary of slang in the Russian language has long been a widespread phenomenon. But when many people

hear this phrase, they immediately think of criminal phrases, which the common man does not immediately understand.

What is slang? Before looking at an example of slang, you need to understand what the term is. So these are words that are only used by certain people. They can be united by one profession, specialty, interests, age, common views, etc. In other words, Russian slang is a completely separate speech that only certain people can understand. And based on this, social groups today have a great variety, and then the slang is correspondingly flourishing. It should be noted that nowadays examples of slang can be found in almost any word. They appear in almost any moderately stable community. For example, slang can be observed in the speech of schoolchildren, students, soldiers, musicians, athletes, alcoholics, criminals, etc. As you can see, the social "spread" is huge. Needless to say, even the expressions of intellectuals can be called jargon with complete confidence - and it will be right. Most people don't know that they use slang words. They are so firmly established in our lives that they have already become common and acceptable expressions, and we pronounce them without hesitation. Take as an example the speech of schoolchildren or students. "Physical", "couple", "exasperated", "annoying", "clear", "didn't understand" etc. - we hear all this every day and understand what these expressions mean. However, there are also "stronger" words. We are talking about the slang of people associated with the criminal sphere. Also called "thieves". Perhaps the most common word in this area is "zone". Everyone has heard this clearly. This, as you can already understand, means prison. By the way, for the sake of justice, it should be noted that thieves and criminal slang are the richest. A truly unique language. "Fart" (luck), "Kent" (close friend), "Olive" (bullet), "Kipishnut" (anger), "Jigan" (desperate) - there are many such words. You don't have to go deep into their meaning - you can already understand that this "language" is really complicated.

So why do such expressions appear - that's clear, but how are they formed? It's actually quite simple. The first way is to borrow money. So, for example, "men" (guy, man), "people" (people, society), etc. entered our modern language. As you may have guessed, the listed words are taken from English. Often they take simple words and revise. "Buzz" means "drink". Why is this special expression? Because this very well emphasizes the duration of the process. There is another popular way, which is to make words. There is a word for "fun" (enjoyment). This is where the slang word "Baldej" (pleasure) comes from. And there are many similar examples. Jargon has always existed and will always exist. This dictionary is in constant contact with the national language, "captures" certain expressions from it and changes them in its own way. The most important thing is to know the measure when using such words. Nevertheless, you should not often block your speech with such expressions. Otherwise, if everyone turns to jargon, we will have to forget the purity of our mighty language.

Result. The interest in learning slang for young people arose from the slang itself. Work on the analysis of "spoken speech" (that is, linguists attached slang to this style of speech) was carried out in the 19th century. For the first time, an attempt to describe and classify the jargon vocabulary was presented in Mikutsky's dictionary (Mikutsky S. Materials for a comparative and explanatory dictionary of the Russian language and other Slavic dialects. - St. Petersburg, 1832). Dahl's popular dictionary provides more information on this topic. From which the explanatory dictionary Vladimir Dahl, as it is known, came from the language of merchants of the slang. Therefore, another slang name is fenya (to work on a hair dryer).

These merchants formed a separate class. And since they always had a variety of goods and money, robbers often attacked them. After that they invented a special language that only they could understand - jargon. There is also an assumption that they originated from the Athenians, an almost extinct people. This nation, which now lives only in legend, was made up of several ethnic groups, including Africans and Greeks. This coded language was passed on to children, grandchildren, and great-grandchildren. And so it was common people. I liked that it gradually began to be used by beggars, horse thieves and ordinary highwaymen, against whom the *fenya* first appeared. But they not only communicated with him, but also verbal and written information, not wanting to reveal secrets and secrets. Such a slang vocabulary appears, the origin of which is closely related to socio-political processes in the entire society. Jargons are lexically and stylistically heterogeneous, and the most common vocabulary is characterized by instability and rapid change. Jargon can appear in any stable and more or less closed community. This is a kind of collective language game, which ends when a person leaves this community (for example, a student who graduates from school and goes to university stops using school slang, but begins to actively use student slang). There are school slang, college slang, army slang, musician slang, sports slang, trade slang, computer slang, junkie slang and more. The most obvious ones are:

1. Slang - youth slang (for example, "curse", "teacher")
2. Argo - the secret language of stratified groups of society - thieves, vagabonds and beggars (L.I. Rahmanova, V.N. Suzdaltsev. Modern Russian language.)
3. Professional jargons (professional languages) - are characterized by highly developed and sufficiently precise terminology of certain crafts, industries, etc. In addition to the slangs that arise on the basis of the national language, there are also slangs that appear as a result of the communication of the multilingual population in border areas (for example, seaports). Scientists distinguish this type of slang as *interslang*. It combines words from different slang. This slang refers to "not one, but many (including long-lost) social groups. Passing from one slang to another, their "common fund" words can change their form and meaning: "dark" in slang - to hide prey, then - "cunning (during interrogation)", modern in youth slang - to speak unclearly, to avoid the answer. In modern language, young people, these slangs are common .

Any vicious circle of communication in which different people find themselves for one reason or another inevitably produces its own language. It can be professional slang, student slang or bully slang. Representatives of the criminal world of Russia have created a unique subculture that inevitably reflects prison life, the specifics of criminal business, and the psychology of prisoners.

Conclusion. The following conclusions were drawn through the analysis in the course of the research: Nonstandard language units are found in any language , such as in English and youth jargon in Russian are specific to the Uzbek youth language too and should be called youth slang. Slang in Uzbek is found not only in oral communication and Internet communication, but also in the language of literary works. In English linguistics, although initially there were negative opinions about these units, modern trends approach to it positively. Slang differs in its origin and synchronous state from the adjacent phenomena - jargon, argot, and cant. In English and Uzbek, slang is seen as a special peripheral lexical layer, which has a broad scope of usage. Its composition is divided into general slang and special slang. General slangs are informal words and phrases that are equally familiar to all

members of the social stratum. Jargon, argot, dialect, etc. that are adjacent to slang are not included in special slang. They are considered to be the independent units of the sociolect. Based on these sources and on our research, we cannot say that the terms slang, jargon, and argot are the same linguistic units specific to vernacular colloquial language. Argot is a word and phrase used to hide the subject of communication in the speech of a narrow social stratum, according to their interests, hobbies, age. They are designed for the purpose of secrecy, and act as a password. Jargon is a word or phrase whose use is limited to a small social group in a profession or other narrow circle, which has a different lexical meaning than the general one, serving only that group. Slang is an emotionally coloured informal means of informal communication that is composed primarily of elements of young people's literary language.

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